

This is the list of matter types:

Gold – ordinary matter, the matter of retardation.

Opal – rainbow matter, the spectrum of truth.

Emerald – dark matter.

Ruby – Dark red matter.

Diamond – social matter.

Nuclear dark matter – the matter of truest psychopathy.

Nuclear white matter – the matter of truest sociopathy.

Mythril – crystal blue matter.

Adamantium – glistening green matter.

Silver – mirror matter.

Fluorite – fluctuation matter.

Vanta matter – phantom matter/ anti-matter.

Marble – no matter/ appearance matter – the matter of illusions, delusions, neurosis, and psychosis.

Corrupted matter – the matter of cancer. Healed by its counter – crystal clear matter.

Sulfur/meth – disappearance matter.

Ghost matter – the matter of mania.

Black matter – the matter of rules. One rule, clear. Two rules, draw. Three rules, dice. Four rules, quit.

Black fluctuation matter – the matter of schizo.

Smime matter – the matter of a living problem.

Smoom matter – the matter of a grandiose delusion. The matter of crust.

Sloom matter – the matter of a grandiose illusion. The matter of perfume.

Floom matter – the matter of grandiose smugness. The matter of fart dust.

Cock matter – the matter of a sleeved inquisitor.

Nuclear faecal matter – the matter of total grandiosity.

Nuclear wax matter – the matter of total psychosis.

Nuclear snot matter – the matter of total neurosis.

Nuclear puss matter – the matter of total murmours.

Nuclear jizz matter – the matter of a flange, of something-not paddle-pop.

Nuclear sweat matter – the matter of a buss, of nothing-not cyclon-bot.

Nuclear anal juice matter – the matter of total identity swap.

Nuclear fungal matter – the matter of total power.

Nuclear alien matter – the matter of a total probe.

Nuclear piss matter – the matter of a total fetish.

Particle matter – the matter of poo.

MDMA – lust matter.

Blank matter – the matter of popping in.

Cocaine – kink matter.

Munce matter – the matter of a munced nug.

Glistening dark matter – the matter of stars.

Video matter – the matter of sleeping.

Cinematic matter – the matter of DeepSleep.

Pube matter – the matter of misplaced hair.

Erotic matter – the matter of an abuser.

British matter – the matter of living interference.

Phono matter – the matter of a copyer.

Radioactive matter – the matter of noise.

Radio brown matter – the matter of trees.

Entropic matter – the matter of no escape.

Australian matter – the matter of seriousness.

American matter – the matter of media.

European matter – the matter of research.

When sunset, then this model is set, of a setless set.